

Breaking barriers to plant team polycultures: A role for PAT, modern machinery and novel products?

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Summary

Plants teams can provide opportunities for improved crop yield stability, reduced pest, disease and weed burdens, and enhanced resilience of agricultural systems. Uptake of polycultural approaches, however, can be prevented by barriers to commercial adoption in the UK, Europe and further afield. Precision Agriculture Technology (PAT) and machinery developments can provide means to overcome barriers that are practical in nature. Discussions with PAT and machinery specialists, and farmers, were conducted, identifying over 40 PAT solutions to plant team barriers. A matrix was developed to group and match these solutions to practical barrier types, demonstrating availability of solutions across both structured and unstructured plant team designs, and across different levels of engagement with PAT approaches. The findings have been structured so as to facilitate use in supporting and informing plant team transitions, by suggesting means of overcoming the practical barriers reported by farming industries.

Key words: Intercropping, plant teams, barriers, precision agriculture technology, machinery, solutions

Introduction

The use of plant teams, and intercropping techniques, as a modern agriculture practice has the potential to promote positive opportunities in current commercial production, by addressing several key challenges associated with modern monocultural systems. Higher productivity of species-rich systems relative to monocultures is often reported (Hector *et al.*, 2010), supported through facilitative mechanisms such as resource sharing and complementarity (Brooker *et al.*, 2015). Pest populations in intercropped systems, for example, can be directly regulated through mechanisms such as altered crop apparency to invading insects (Finch & Collier, 2012), while greater diversity and complexity of resources can support not only pollinator populations (Potts *et al.*, 2003), but also those of pest natural enemies, leading to potential reductions in crop damage (Letourneau *et al.*, 2011). The suppression of plant pathogens, and reduced disease incidence, has also been reported in polyculture, with factors such as decreased host availability, microclimate effects and dispersal alterations influencing establishment and spread (Boudreau, 2013). Also, of critical importance, is the ability of species-rich systems to buffer against environmental fluctuations, increasing overall agricultural system resilience to stresses such as climate change and market pressures (Brooker *et al.*, 2015).

Plant teams formed the basis of many early agricultural systems, and in many regions, such as Latin America (Francis, 1986), Africa (Brooker *et al.*, 2015; Cook *et al.*, 2007), or, historically, China (Brooker *et al.*, 2015), intercropping remains an important production method. In many cases, current use is characterised by low mechanisation, low input, high labour, and subsistence agriculture. In European systems, the advent of high input, highly mechanised monocultural approaches has led to comparative rarity of polyculture in mainstream farming, although intercropping remains used in agroforestry systems and, often, organic production. The potential benefits of polyculture, however, have led to a resurgence of interest in plant team usage, including among conventional farmers; here especially, however, previous reliance on current monocultural production models in mainstream farming have led to practical barriers (among others) that limit plant team uptake and implementation. For at least some of these practical barriers, Precision Agriculture Technology (PAT), machinery development and novel products may provide available or near-market solutions able to ease transitions to intercropping approaches, supporting and promoting the commercial uptake of plant teams in the agricultural industry across the UK and Europe.

As part of the EU-H2020 DIVERSify project, a programme of work has been undertaken to identify barriers to plant team uptake in UK and European agricultural production systems, using a participatory approach. Stakeholders were engaged through a series of fifteen international stakeholder meetings in eleven countries (across Europe, Kenya, and Palestine), and were consulted to explore and define perceived and realised barriers to plant team uptake in each region (Pearce *et al.*, 2018). Subsequently, practical barriers were distilled from the workshop findings, and examined in greater detail (Tippin *et al.*, 2019*a,b*). The present paper describes the steps taken to translate previous exploratory work conducted in the project into available or near-market solutions to overcome barriers to uptake. Practical, physical barriers where PAT and machinery developments might provide a means of overcoming cropping complexities were identified from previous project outputs, forming the basis for discussions with machinery manufacturers, farmers, industry representatives and specialists to identify specific solutions (George *et al.*, 2020*a*). The information gathered from these activities has been organised and formulated into a matrix of solutions, to highlight the roles of specific PAT, machinery developments and novel products in overcoming barriers to plant team uptake.

Materials and Methods

The barrier-related outputs of the DIVERSify international stakeholder workshops (Pearce *et al.*, 2018), were distilled and examined in greater detail (Tippin *et al.*, 2019*a*). Practical, physical barriers were discussed therein, with distinction made between whether barriers were considered solved, unsolved, or perceived. This information was also collated with the observations and experiences of Participatory Farmers, a network of farmers subcontracted by tender to the DIVERSify project to conduct on-farm trials using plant teams of interest to their individual businesses. These previous outputs were reviewed, and formed the basis of discussions and information gathering activities on PAT, machinery and other solutions to practical plant team barriers therein identified.

Defining practical barrier types

Based on the preceding outputs, practical plant team barriers identified were broadly categorised as dividing into one of four subdivisions, relating to challenges associated with: (a) drilling (e.g. differences in seed sizes and handling requirements), (b) agronomy (e.g. differences in competition, nutrition or pest control requirements), (c) harvest (e.g. timing of and separation requirements), and (d) planning (or other barriers). Identification of barriers into specific groups allowed for targeted discussions to take place on specific solutions that might exist, or be in development, for specific challenges.

Data gathering and survey of specialist manufacturers and distributors

Information and data were gathered on potential solutions through multiple complementary routes between March 2018 and March 2020. Direct canvassing of the DIVERSify project consortium partner base and Participatory Farmer network allowed detail to be requested on solutions known to, and where relevant used by, partners or their contacts and networks when working with plant teams. This also allowed access to partner industry knowledge in terms of on-farm machinery modifications and developments. One-to-one discussions, either in person or by telephone, were also arranged with identified PAT and machinery specialists of interest, to discuss solutions to plant team barriers. Finally, discussions were also held with PAT and machinery specialist company representatives at three major and two minor industry Agri-Tech events.

In order to ensure sufficient detail was gathered from the DIVERSify partner base, and to facilitate note-taking and recording of supporting evidence from one-to-one discussions, a data capture form was developed and circulated to project partners and industry representatives engaged in the data gathering phase of the work. In addition to providing context for the data gathering exercise to support provision of responses, the form allowed for free-form text provision in a table subdividing between the broad category classifications, as well as defined subcategories for each barrier type, should this level of detail be available.

The data gathering process resulted in the return of two formally completed data forms, two telephone interviews, eight one-to-one meetings, and direct engagement with *c.* 40 PAT and machinery companies across attended industry events.

Collation of survey and one-to-one discussions responses, and solution categorisation

Details on the general and specific PAT, machinery and product solutions to practical barriers of implementing plant teams, as returned in data capture forms, interviews and discussions conducted, were collated and listed by overall barrier type (George *et al.*, 2020a). It deserves note that, throughout the present work, only solutions that address challenges of using plant teams overlapping fully both temporally and spatially were included. Each solution was individually examined and grouped according to whether it could be used to overcome barriers when implementing: (a) unstructured plant teams (e.g. companion crops, green understories), or (b) structured plant teams (e.g. formal intercropping, strip-tilled green understories). In cases where a given solution could be applied to both unstructured and structured plant teams, it was listed in both groupings. Solutions were also assigned a further classification, indicating whether they could be described as: (i) accessible (i.e. suited to most operations, and implementable by most end users with minimal investment), (ii) available (i.e. implementable with some prior engagement in PAT or high levels of investment machinery solutions), or (iii) attainable (i.e. implementable or theoretically available, but only with highly specialised equipment; not yet widely accessible).

Results

Solutions for barriers in unstructured plants teams

Eighteen generic solutions resolving barriers to uptake in unstructured plant teams were identified (Fig. 1a). These represented solutions within all four broad barrier categories, and included 12 machinery, four novel product, and three PAT solutions (one of which overlapped with one machinery solution). As several solutions resolved challenges in multiple barrier subdivision types, a total of 29 specific barrier solutions were reported.

Solutions for barriers in structured plant teams

In the case of structured plant teams, 27 generic solutions resolving 55 specific barriers to uptake in structured plant teams were identified (Fig. 1b), with several resolving challenges across multiple barrier subdivision types. Of these, 19 machinery, 10 PAT, and four novel product solutions were reported, with solutions suggested across all four broad barrier categories. There was overlap between six machinery and PAT solutions.

Fig. 1. Solutions identified to address practical barriers to commercial uptake and implementation in (a) unstructured and (b) structured plant teams. Solutions have been subdivided into whether they can be considered accessible (dark grey; suited to most operations, and implementable by most end users with minimal investment), available (medium grey; implementable with some prior engagement in PAT or high levels of investment machinery solutions), or attainable (light grey; implementable or theoretically available but only with highly specialised equipment, not yet widely accessible).

Discussion

Solutions that were accessible, or, at least, available, were identified for all barrier categories in the case of both plant team designs. Unstructured plant teams should, at least theoretically, represent less of a challenge in terms of drilling, given reduced reliance on spatial structure and thus decreased reliance on high-investment machinery or PAT. In-crop management, however, might be expected to incur greater complexities (of competition and yield suppression, or pest, pathogen and weed burdens), as might harvest and processing of harvested material, owing to complete mixing of plant team components. Conversely, although structured plants might simplify in-crop management and, potentially, harvest challenges through spatial separation of plant targets, it could also be expected that drilling, management and harvesting of plant teams grown in this way would require greater capital investment in machinery and PAT that facilitate implementation of pre-determined spatial designs.

It is particularly encouraging to note that an important proportion of solutions, 62% in unstructured and 47% for structured plant teams respectively, could be classed as readily accessible for industry implementation. These generic solutions included, as examples, the potential to repurpose existing equipment, such as fertiliser spreaders or combi-drills (either 'as is' or with minor modifications, including additional hopper attachments), to drill multiple plant species, or to use desiccants to address crop maturity differences at time of harvest. Novel products, such as low risk biopesticides with blanket approvals for selected crops in some countries, were suggested by specialists as a means of addressing pest and disease concerns. Certain solutions may, however, present risk elsewhere. Large machinery, for example direct or combi-drills, capable of handling the challenges of multiple seeding rates, sowing depths, and seed sizes, may overcome drilling barriers, but might equally lead to compaction concerns in heavier soils. Furthermore, solutions may also only be relevant for certain plant team combinations, for example where issues of specific novel product registration are concerned, or where machinery specifically targets plant teams with separation of species by height. This in mind, plant team partner selection also presents an opportunity in itself to overcome barriers to plant team uptake. Component species can be targeted to facilitate use of available solutions, or to deliver specific agronomic benefits, such as weed suppression or pest and pathogen control, thus removing those aspects as a barrier to plant team implementation.

The data gathered on solutions to barriers also suggests a greater availability of solutions for structured compared to unstructured plant team designs (a total of 55 vs 29, respectively). Differences in the number of agronomic solutions, accounting for near 70% of the overall difference, drive this. Given that these primarily relate to species-specific crop inputs, spatial separation facilitates and maximises availability of PAT solutions that allow application or targeting of specific products to high accuracy. Furthermore, PAT-assisted placement technologies, that permit precise placement of seed, support management of competition between plant team species components, as well as enabling future application of other inputs. Overall, the findings suggest that barriers to plant team uptake can be overcome where plant teams are unstructured, but that use of structured cropping designs, particularly where coupled with PAT approaches and modern machinery, can further facilitate implementation. Conversely, however, a greater proportion of accessible solutions, (i.e. those that can be implemented with minimal additional investment by farmers, or which use existing machinery), can be applied to unstructured plant teams, whereas use of structured plant team designed requires greater investment in machinery and PAT engagement.

A detailed report, including further consideration of solutions with greater category refinement of the four different barrier types, was produced and reported in George *et al.* (2020b) and is being prepared for publication elsewhere (Banfield-Zanin *et al.*, in prep). This includes tabulation and formulation of identified specific solutions into a matrix format. In this format, navigation should be simplified for industry stakeholders and end-users, with an aim to facilitate use in supporting and informing plant team transitions as relevant to specific business interests and levels of PAT engagement and investment.

The findings of this study have demonstrated that practical solutions to facilitate polycultural practices exist at varying levels of accessibility across all barrier categories, for both unstructured and structured plant team designs. These include roles for PAT and modern machinery solutions, with deployment of the latter often being dependent on engagement with the former. Regardless, whilst access to and engagement with PAT approaches appear likely to facilitate intercropping, many barriers can be addressed through machinery, and novel product solutions, independently of PAT uptake. The greater number of solutions that can be applied to structured plant teams, however, also suggest that barriers may be more readily overcome by existing, near-market technologies, where adoption of spatial structuring facilitates delivery of solutions through PAT placement technologies. Finally, judicious selection of plant team components themselves also represent a solution to barriers, insofar as these can address, in particular, agronomic challenges such as pest, pathogen and weed burden control.

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